

SYNCLUSIVE

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Policy brief #2

Regional Coalitions for Inclusive Labour Markets Insights from the SYNCLUSIVE Project

**SYNCLUSIVE: System approach to
close the employment gap and
create a more inclusive labour
market for vulnerable groups**

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Key findings

This second SYNCLUSIVE policy brief draws on experiences from four national Living Labs (Bulgaria, Finland, the Netherlands, Portugal). It explores how coalition-based strategies can address multi-level systemic labour market barriers so that vulnerable groups can access sustainable employment opportunities and progress in the labour market.

Across Europe, vulnerable groups (like young or older people, migrants, long-term unemployed people) face interrelated barriers to labour market inclusion across individual, organisational, and systemic levels. They often result in fragmented service provision, mismatched priorities, and governance gaps. For instance, SMEs may focus on short-term staffing needs, while larger organisations as well as public actors pursue longer-term goals.

Regional coalitions combine efforts of municipalities, employers, training providers, worker representative bodies and civil society organisations to jointly develop, adapt and implement interventions, such as job-seeking training, on-the-job learning, peer learning and fast-track training. They also help to navigate and connect fragmented systems. Employers play a crucial role in such regional coalitions—providing jobs, work trials, on-the-job training, and supporting workplace integration. Their early and structural involvement ensures interventions meet real labour market needs, though engagement remains challenging, especially when short-term benefits are unclear.

To ensure continued relevance and impact, coalitions engage in regular cycles of joint reflection and adjustment—identifying shared challenges, agreeing on improvement actions, tracking progress, and adapting interventions based on what works in practice. This collective, action-oriented learning process helps coalitions stay responsive and aligned as they work toward sustainable solutions. Building on coalitions of the willing and gradually helps maintain momentum and may further expand engagement.

Tailored strategies, such as involving sector organisations, business networks, or recruitment agencies can improve access to employers and enhance coalition effectiveness. This is particularly relevant for SMEs, which often face time and capacity constraints, and have doubts about the value of activities beyond day-to-day operations and require low-threshold, clearly beneficial ways to participate. Coalition benefit from adaptive leadership—characterised by clear coordination, flexible role division, and the ability to respond to political or organisational shifts. Informal trust-building must be balanced with structured decision-making, and reflection moments to improve responsiveness and sustain collaboration.

To accelerate progress, policymakers could embed coalition-based approaches in EU and national policy frameworks, ensure stable funding for coordination, and provide support for inclusive governance models that promote shared ownership and adaptability.

System approach to close the employment gap

Within SYNCLUSIVE, customised sets of interventions at various labour market levels are designed and implemented by a variety of regional stakeholders: the regional coalitions.

Why regional coalitions? Consider the story of Fatima, a motivated woman with a migrant background who aspires to work in childcare—a sector with staff shortages. Despite her motivation and relevant informal skills as a parent, she lacks formal qualifications, has language barriers and is unfamiliar with the local training and job placement systems. On her own, she cannot navigate the fragmented support landscape. No single actor—be it the municipality, a training institute, the worker nor her representative or an employer—can offer the needed support for sustainable employment alone. Only through a regional coalition that aligns employers, workers and their representatives, training providers, and social services, tailored solutions can be developed. Similarly, Maria—a 56-year-old woman with a higher education background—wants to return to work after several years of caregiving. She encountered digital skill gaps, uncertainty about her employability, and age-related discrimination from employers. A regional coalition can coordinate retraining, coaching, and employer outreach—creating a tailored pathway back into the labour market that no single organisation could provide alone.

Examples illustrating that without structured collaboration, initiatives risk being ineffective, fragmented or unsustainable:

- **Bulgaria:** Older workers, with a focus on women (50+), struggled with digital skill gaps and employer biases. Regional collaboration brought together municipal services, training providers, recruitment and news agencies, trade unions and employers to coordinate retraining and create trust-based hiring channels.
- **Finland:** Long-term unemployed people face numerous challenges, including low professional skills, impaired health and work ability, and low self-efficacy, job searching skills and motivation to gain employment. Simultaneously, employers are often hesitant to hire them. By leveraging a regional coalition, these employment barriers can be addressed through collaborative efforts among service providers, combining e.g., job coaching and training services for both job seekers and employers.
- **Netherlands:** Employers lacked the knowledge and capacity to support low-skilled or migrant workers' skill development, while legal barriers and language issues complicated access. Only through a regional coalition these gaps could be addressed simultaneously by linking legal expertise, employer coaching, and tailored training.
- **Portugal:** Youth encountered mismatches between their qualifications and job requirements, compounded by limited work experience and discrimination. Cross-sector collaboration allowed for jointly adapted and implemented training and work-based learning pathways tailored to real employer needs.

The regional coalitions engaged in regular cycles of identifying shared challenges, agreeing on solutions, tracking progress, and developing or adapting interventions based on what works in practice. This collective, action-oriented learning process helped coalitions stay responsive and aligned and let to the key activities shown in Box 1.

Box 1: Overview of SYNCLUSIVE Living Labs

Country	Target Group	Coalition Composition	Key Activities
 Bulgaria	50+ workers, with a focus on women	Municipality, Employers, training providers, trade unions, News agency, recruitment agency	Awareness building, tailored retraining, psychological support, peer-learning, matching
 Finland	Long-term unemployed	Municipality, training institutes, NGO, employers, associations of SMEs, Wellbeing Services County	Employment support, peer-learning, developmental-oriented leadership
 Netherlands	Migrant women and practically schooled workers	Municipality, Employee Insurance Agency, Vocational Education Cooperation Foundation, employer, training institutes	Accelerated training, on-the-job training, developmental-oriented leadership, matching
 Portugal	Youth (<=35 years)	Three different once including: Municipality, universities, training institutes, employers, Temporary Work Company, Incubator, consultancy, Science, Business & technology networks	Innovative training, internships, match

Benefits of regional coalitions

SYNCLUSIVE's preliminary findings indicate the following benefits of regional coalitions:

- **Integrated intervention design:** Coalitions enabled the development and implementation of comprehensive intervention packages that could only be done through collaboration between multiple stakeholders—such as training providers, employers, worker representatives and employment and social services—resulting in integrated solutions that single actors could not achieve alone.
- **Improved stakeholder alignment:** Regular coordination between municipalities, employers, worker representatives, training providers, and civil society organisations increased coherence in both strategy and implementation of interventions targeting inclusion of vulnerable groups.
- **Lowering employer barriers for inclusion:** Employers may become more willing to engage with vulnerable job seekers when supported by coalitions that offer shared responsibility, practical support, and simplified procedures.
- **Tailored and accelerated learning pathways:** Coalitions supported fast-track, practice-oriented routes to employment—especially valuable for low-skilled individuals or those requiring on-the-job learning.
- **Building trust and sustainable collaboration in the region:** Repeated interaction across organisations fostered trust, mutual understanding, and stronger foundations for long-term cooperation in the region beyond individual projects.

Box 2: Coalition Building Theory

The SYNCLUSIVE project uses two complementary frameworks to guide the formation and strengthening of regional coalitions.

Community Coalition Action Theory (CCAT)

CCAT outlines coalitions as a basis for more effective implementation of practice-based initiatives (Butterfoss & Kegler, 2002; Granner & Sharpe, 2004; Kegler, Rigler & Honeycutt, 2010; Zakocs & Edwards, 2006). It identifies cyclical phases for the development, (re)design and implementation of intervention packages aimed at achieving the shared goal of sustainable labour market inclusion of vulnerable groups. SYNCLUSIVE coalitions typically follow this cycle: they start informally, with flexible stakeholder engagement in a ‘coalition of the willing’ (*formation*), evolve into more structured planning and implementation oriented collaborative framework (*maintenance*), and gradually work toward embedding successful strategies in existing ecosystems (*institutionalisation*). For example, in the Bulgarian Living Lab, the coalition began with informal stakeholder meetings and later signed a non-binding cooperation agreement to formalise collaboration.

Learning, Innovation, Structuring, Organising (LISO) framework

LISO builds on CCAT and translates it into the labour market context (Pannebakker, Kuiper & Gonçalves-Prins, 2025). It supports coalitions in overcoming fragmentation and managing complexity by encouraging:

- Facilitating shared learning and reflection
- Stimulating innovation through co-creation
- Clarifying roles and structuring collaboration
- Organising cooperation in line with institutional complexity.

For example, the Dutch and Portuguese coalitions applied LISO principles by investing in mutual learning and iterative co-design sessions, which gradually led to shared problem definitions and a jointly structured intervention strategy.

Pathways for Upscaling

Together, CCAT and LISO offer a strong foundation for structured, adaptive, and scalable collaboration. Their phased and reflective approach fosters local ownership while allowing tested models to be adapted and replicated across sectors and regions—laying the groundwork for sustainable system innovation.

Overview of SYNCLUSIVE Regional Coalitions

The table below summarises how each Living Lab addresses coalition building along key CCAT dimensions, including barriers and contextual adjustments:

CCAT Element	Netherlands	Finland	Portugal	Bulgaria
Formation	Informal one-on-one stakeholder engagement first; followed by co-creation session.	Started from an existing public sector network with established bilateral collaborations; the biggest regional employers were asked to join with poor success.	Structured launch with clear goals with core of coalition members, later expansion to other partners is aimed for.	Started informally; reinforced by signing coalition agreement.

CCAT Element	Netherlands	Finland	Portugal	Bulgaria
Maintenance	Sustained by municipal commitment and sector focus; flexible structure.	Core group remained small; strong but mainly bilateral collaboration; some new members joined (NGO, association of SMEs); employers' role remains limited.	Maintained through continuous support from coordinating party and regular updates.	Maintained through formal planning and sector-specific implementation.
Barriers	Legal ambiguity; limited employer time; leadership instability.	Mainly SMEs in region, difficult to engage; rising unemployment; reform of employment policy at municipal level.	In some regions there are many SMEs, particularly difficult to engage; lack of clear incentives and funding for employers.	Political instability; agreement non-binding; initial employer hesitancy.
Leadership	Municipality-led with researcher support; adaptable but sensitive to turnover.	Leadership disrupted by local government changes and sensitive to turnover. Research partner has taken a bigger role for promoting collaboration.	Leadership was generally clear and stable, with defined coordination roles. Still, continuous close leadership to maintain engagement of all stakeholders was challenging.	Informal leadership stabilised by formal agreement and shared goals; proactive role of coordinator.
Engagement	Active in core group; employer involvement improved with sector focus.	Core public sector actors are engaged; many actors engage in bilateral cooperation regardless of the project, limited private-sector role.	Balanced public-private mix with sectoral clarity.	Formalised roles encouraged participation; building relationships with stakeholders an important incentive for members.

These insights confirm the importance of adapting coalition approaches to the local context while maintaining the core principles of CCAT. Formalisation, employer engagement, and continuity of leadership remain key challenges and enablers depending on governance culture, institutional stability, and sectoral focus.

Key cross-cutting lessons:

- **Leadership clarity is essential but vulnerable:** Changes in political or organisational leadership exposed vulnerabilities in coalition coordination —most notably in Finland, but also observed, though to a lesser extent, in the Netherlands. This highlighted the need for shared leadership models and stable coordination structures.
- **Employer engagement requires clear value and simplicity:** Across all Living Labs, operational constraints, limited time, and unclear direct benefits hindered employer participation. Engagement improved when coalitions co-designed interventions with employers and focused on concrete sectoral needs. Particularly for SMEs, participation requires practical

formats and tangible and (also) short term benefits—such as shared support models in which coalition partners take over non-core tasks like training, pre-selection, or skills development, resulting in clearer returns such as solving staffing shortages. Continued adaptation and experimentation are needed to identify engagement approaches that deliver immediate, recognisable value.

- **Trust grows informally, but commitment needs structure:** Informal interaction helped establish initial trust and engagement, while formal mechanisms—such as coalition agreements (e.g. Bulgaria)—provided continuity and shared responsibility. In addition, embedding regular learning moments and stakeholder feedback improves adaptability of the coalition.
- **Sector-specific coalitions increase focus and uptake:** Sectoral orientation (e.g. childcare in the Netherlands) helped match interventions to employer needs and enhanced participation.
- **Balancing structure and flexibility require cultural sensitivity:** Effective coalitions found a context-sensitive balance between informal collaboration and formal coordination. In more hierarchical or rules-oriented governance cultures, clearly defined roles and separate responsibilities may work better; in less hierarchical and more participatory cultures, co-creation and shared ownership are key. This balance is essential for both legitimacy and impact—and may benefit from further cross-national comparison.
- **Not everyone needs to be involved at once:** Coalitions of the willing—starting with committed actors and expanding gradually—can deliver more meaningful progress than overly inclusive approaches.

Policy recommendations

Inclusive labour markets require more than isolated projects—they need strategic, well-coordinated collaboration at the regional level. The recommendations below are grouped into three categories to support different aspects of system change.

System and Policy Structure

Create an enabling policy and funding environment to embed coalition-based approaches.

- **Explicitly support regional coalitions in national and EU policy frameworks**

Recognise and integrate regional, coalition-based approaches to labour market inclusion within major national and EU policy frameworks—such as in national labour market initiatives and legislation and in the European Pillar of Social Rights and the Pact for Skills. This signals long-term policy support and fosters continuity across Member States.
- **Fund and incentivise regional coordination and collaboration**

Allocate structural and targeted funding for coalition development, coordination, and facilitation via national and EU instruments like ESF+, Erasmus+, and the Just Transition Fund. Consider launching dedicated calls for multi-stakeholder innovation and collaboration in labour market inclusion.

- **Invest in capacity building for local governments and other regional stakeholders in leading coalitions**

Strengthen the long-term capabilities of municipalities and other regional actors to lead inclusive labour market coalitions by offering sustained training, technical support, and long-term financial support.

- **Stimulate context-sensitive monitoring and evaluation**

Develop flexible frameworks and indicators for tracking coalition outcomes and learning, while allowing adaptation to regional contexts to support learning, comparability, and accountability.

Coalition Practice and Adaptive Processes

Build learning, ownership, and trust within coalitions.

- **Embed joint learning, co-creation and action cycles in coalition practice**

Encourage coalitions to identify challenges collaboratively, define and implement solutions, track progress, and adapt accordingly. This action-oriented cycle enhances engagement, practical problem-solving, and responsiveness. While not all stakeholders need to be equally involved at every stage, maintaining a co-creative mindset throughout ensures shared ownership and relevance of outcomes.

- **Ensure inclusive and adaptive governance combined with informal trust building**

Promote balanced stakeholder representation, and flexible leadership structures adapted to regional realities. Combine informal trust-building with structured decision-making - drawing inspiration from frameworks like CCAT and LISO - to enhance legitimacy and ownership. Start with coalitions of the willing and invest in building trust and ownership over time.

Stakeholder Engagement and Support

Ensure active involvement of employers and other regional actors with shared responsibilities.

- **Encourage employer engagement through practical incentives and shared responsibility**

Support employer participation by clearly communicating the benefits for employers—such as addressing staff shortages, improving retention, and receiving practical support through coalitions. Particularly for SMEs, participation is more feasible when tasks like pre-selection, candidate training, or mentoring are shared with other coalition actors. Ensure engagement formats are low-threshold, time-efficient, and co-designed with employers so they recognise the direct relevance to their organisational needs.

- **Stimulate sector-focused collaboration to tackle pressing labour market needs and support SMEs**

Use regional coalitions to respond to specific sectoral challenges—such as personnel shortages in care or mismatches in the digital economy—by facilitating and aligning employer demand with inclusive training and recruitment pathways.

SYNCLUSIVE shows that inclusive labour markets can only be built through collaboration. Regional coalitions offer a practical and scalable way to overcome fragmentation, tailor solutions, and deliver lasting impact.

How to get in touch with the SYNCLUSIVE team?

The SYNCLUSIVE team remains committed to its ongoing efforts in the coming years, aiming to engage anyone interested in enhancing the labour market position of vulnerable groups. With a strong social media presence on platforms like X and LinkedIn, and our website, we welcome your participation. Additionally, we disseminate our work through various activities and events. Join us in shaping a more inclusive labour market by reaching out via our communication channels – we're just a click away from starting the conversation.

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SYNCLUSIVE Project Identity

Project name	System approach to close the employment gap and create a more inclusive labor market for vulnerable groups
Project acronym	SYNCLUSIVE
Coordinator	NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO, The Netherlands
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